

scheme of oxidation may be considered as follows :

The rate of oxidation could obviously be given by rate of disappearance of hexacyanoferrate(III) as shown in step (II), i.e.,

$$-\frac{d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]}{dt} = k_2 [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}][\text{S}] \quad \dots \text{ (1)}$$

The net rate of oxidation of levulinic acid thus can be obtained on substituting the value of [S] from step (I) in eqn. (1) and is given as

$$-\frac{d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]}{dt} = k_2 K [\text{S}][\text{OH}^-][\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] \quad \dots \text{ (2)}$$

where K is the equilibrium constant and S is substrate anion. At constant [S] and [OH⁻], k₂K[S][OH⁻] can be replaced by pseudo first order rate constant k₁.

The observed first order dependence of the reaction on each hexacyanoferrate(III), levulinic acid and hydroxide ion concentration is obvious from the equation (2). The rate determining step would involve interaction between two negatively charged ions [obvious from step (II)]. For this step a positive salt effect is expected. The effect of ionic strength of the medium on reaction rate was studied by employing different concentrations of potassium chloride (Table I). Our experimental results are in complete agreement with the above facts.

In most of the oxidation reactions hexacyanoferrate(III) resembles Cu(II) which involves free radical formation and rapidly oxidises it⁴⁻⁶. Hexacyanoferrate(III)-hexacyanoferrate(II) system, which has higher redox potential than Cu(II)-Cu(I), substantiates better possibility of the rapid oxidation of the free radical with hexacyanoferrate(III) in the alkaline medium and the rapid oxidation of the free radicals might completely mask the polymerisation. Sometimes the vinyl compounds themselves are oxidised under the experimental conditions used

and the test for free radicals fails⁷. Moreover, no spectrophotometric test for complex formation was observed.

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Baeyer-Villiger Oxidation of Steroidal Ketones-V

SHAFIULLAH* and M. A. GHAFFARI

Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh-202 001, India

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IN continuation of our reports on Baeyer-Villiger oxidation of steroidal ketones¹⁻⁴, we subjected compounds (I-IV) to perbenzoic acid oxidation in the presence of *p*-toluenesulphonic acid, as catalyst. A number of anticipated products were successfully isolated from 4-substituted derivatives of cholest-5-en-3-one (I-II) and cholest-4-en-3-one (III-IV).

Experimental

General Procedure for the oxidation of ketone (I-IV):

To a solution of ketone (1 g) in chloroform (12 ml) was added a chloroform solution of perbenzoic acid (2.5 moles) and a few crystals of *p*-toluenesulphonic acid. After allowing the reaction mixture to stand at room temperature for a week, the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The residue was extracted with ether, the ethereal solution was washed with sodium bicarbonate (5%), water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The solvent was evaporated. The oil (~0.8 g) thus obtained was chromatographed over silica gel (20 g). Elution with pet. ether: ether provided the compounds (Table 1).

TABLE I

Com-pounds	Solvent ratio pet. ether : ether	M.P. °C	Yield [%]	Formula	Analysis% C	Found (Calcd.) H
(V)	25 : 1	84	20	C ₃₁ H ₅₂ O ₂	81.70 (81.57)	11.4 (11.4)
(VI)	25 : 1	144	10	C ₂₉ H ₄₈ O ₂	81.61 (81.32)	11.28 (11.21)
(VII)	24 : 1	187	15	—	—	—
(VIII)	20 : 1	96	15	C ₂₉ H ₄₈ O ₂	81.70 (81.32)	10.95 (11.21)
(IX)	13 : 1	112	15	C ₂₉ H ₄₈ O ₂	77.98 (78.40)	10.66 (10.80)
(X)	18 : 1	125	10	C ₂₈ H ₄₆ O ₂	80.80 (81.10)	11.21 (11.20)
(XI)	9 : 1	120	7	C ₂₈ H ₄₆ O ₂	78.20 (78.10)	10.70 (10.80)
(XII)	16 : 1	158	10	—	—	—

Results and Discussion

The compound (I) on treatment with 2.5 moles of perbenzoic acid (*p*-toluenesulphonic acid in catalytic amount) furnished a product m.p. 84°, C₃₁H₅₂O₂. This molecular composition suggests the addition of an oxygen atom to the parent compound (I). The i.r. spectrum of the compound gave bands at 1710 (>C=O) and 875 cm⁻¹ (epoxide).

In n.m.r. spectrum* the absence of vinylic proton and presence of doublet at δ 2.91d (J_{a,e}=5Hz) integrating for one proton, ascribable for C₆-βH, account for the formation of 5α, 6-epoxy-4,4-diethyl-5α-cholestan-3-one(V).

The compound (II) under similar conditions provided two isomeric epoxides, m.pts. 144° and 187°, analysed for C₂₉H₄₈O₂. In the i.r. spectrum of the compound m.p. 144°, bands were seen at 1710 (>C=O) and 720 cm⁻¹ (epoxide). No band for double bond was observed. In the n.m.r. spectrum

the signal observed at δ2.93d (J_{a,e}=5Hz) integrating for one proton is assigned for C₆-βH

The i.r. spectrum of the compound m.p. 187°, exhibited bands at 1700 (>C=O) and 805 cm⁻¹ (epoxide). The n.m.r. spectrum gave a multiplet at δ3.06 integrating for one proton assignable to C₆-αH. On the basis of spectral data the compound m.p. 144° has been assigned the structure as 5, 6α-epoxy-4,4-dimethyl-5α-cholestan-3-one(VI) and compound (VII) m.p. 187° as β-isomer of (VI).

The compound (III) on perbenzoic acid (2.5 moles) oxidation furnished two products of m. pts. 96° and 112°. The compound, m.p. 96°, analysed for C₂₉H₄₈O₂ and the i.r. spectrum showed bands at 1700 (>C=O), 790 cm⁻¹ (epoxide). Only methyl signals were observed in the n.m.r. spectrum of the compound. The epoxide has been shown to be an α-oriented on the mechanistic ground⁵ as well as from previous observations⁶. Thus the compound m.p. 96° is 4α, 5-epoxy-4β-ethyl-5α-cholestan-3-one (VIII). The i.r. spectrum of the compound (IX), m.p. 112° with molecular composition C₂₉H₄₈O₂, exhibited bands at 1700 (>C=O) and 1750 cm⁻¹ (δ-Lactone Carbonyl). The n.m.r. spectrum showed a multiplet centred at δ2.4(4H, ascribable to α-methylene protons). The propanyl derivative (IX) may be due to the acid catalysed rearrangement of the intermediate (XIII) (Scheme 1). Such type of intermediate was also suggested by Pinhey and Schaffner⁷. The structure (IX) as 5β-propanyl-4-oxa-5β-cholestan-3-one was further substantiated by conversion of (VIII) to (IX) on treatment with perbenzoic acid under similar conditions.

Scheme—1

The compound (IV) on similar oxidation afforded known compounds(X), m.p. 125°, (XI), m.p. 120° and (XII), m.p. 158° (identical in all respect)⁷.

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Chemical Investigation of the Leaves of *Phlogacanthus thyrsiflorus*

S. K. BANERJEE, S. BISWAS and M. K. CHOUDHURY

Department of Chemistry, Bose Institute, Calcutta-9

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*PHLOGACANTHUS thyrsiflorus*¹ (family Acanthaceae) is used medicinally like *Adhatoda vasica* which has been reported to be expectorant and mild bronchial antiseptic². The present communication reports the isolation of β -sitosterol, lupeol and betulin from the leaves of *P. thyrsiflorus*.

The petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) extract of the air-dried leaves of *P. thyrsiflorus* on column chromatography over silica gel furnished three compounds designated as compounds A, B and C.

Compound A: $C_{29}H_{50}O$ (M^+ 414), m.p. 136-37° (EtOH), $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 35.6$ ($CHCl_3$), gave a violet to green colour in the Lieberman-Burchard test indicating it to be a phytosterol. On heating with acetic anhydride and pyridine on steam bath it yielded an acetate, $C_{31}H_{52}O_2$ (M^+ 456) m.p. 127-28°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 41.4$ ($CHCl_3$). The identity of compound A with β -sitosterol was confirmed by

comparison of m.p., m.m.p., optical rotation and TLC with an authentic sample.

Compound B: $C_{30}H_{50}O$ (M^+ 426), m.p. 211-12°. It gave a violet to pink colour in the Lieberman-Burchard test indicating it to be a terpenoid. On heating with acetic anhydride and pyridine on steam bath it yielded a monoacetate, $C_{32}H_{52}O_2$ (M^+ 468), m.p. 213-15°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 41.7$ ($CHCl_3$). The identities of compound B and its acetate with lupeol and its acetate respectively were established by comparison (m.p., m.m.p., TLC and IR) with authentic samples,

Compound C: $C_{30}H_{50}O_2$ (M^+ 442), m.p. 258°. It showed violet-pink colour in the Lieberman-Burchard test. Its mass spectral fragmentation pattern was found to be very similar to that of betulin³. On heating with acetic anhydride and pyridine on steam bath it furnished a diacetate, $C_{34}H_{54}O_4$ (M^+ 526) m.p. 222°. Compound C was identified as betulin by comparison of m.p., m.m.p., TLC and IR spectra with an authentic sample of betulin.

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